

UOT 81'367

**THE INTERPRETATION OF THE TOPIC “ADJECTIVE” IN THE WORK
“SHARHU RADI ALAL-KAFIYAH FI ILMIN-NAHW WAL-IRAB”**

VALIYEVA KUBRA SABIR GIZI

Head of the Laboratory,
Nakhchivan Branch of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences.
Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan.

***Abstract.** Prominent scholars of Arabic grammatical schools have offered original insights into nahw (Arabic syntax) and produced seminal works. One of the most influential works in Arabic linguistics is “al-Kafiyah” by Ibn al-Hajib (1175–1249). More than a hundred commentaries have been written on “al-Kafiyah” in Arabic, Persian, and Turkic, including one by Ibn al-Hajib himself. Among these commentaries, “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah fi ilmin-nahw wal-irab” by Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi (?-1287) and “al-Fawaidud-Diyaiyyah” by Molla Jami (?-1492) are the most well-known.*

The work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah”, which covers the syntax section (nahw) of Arabic grammar, is remarkable for Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi’s methodologically comprehensive and insightful approach to grammatical explanations and his scholarly views.

This article examines in detail the scientific views of Ibn al-Hajib and Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi regarding possessive noun phrases (majrurat), as well as the subcategories tawabi (words dependent in inflection), and nat (adjectival forms) in the work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah”.

As a result of the research, the author concludes that “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah” still preserves its significance today due to the richness and originality of its grammatical information and scientific insights. This work is considered one of the major achievements of Arabic linguistic scholarship in the 13th century.

***Key words:** “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah”, the Arabic language, genitive case, adjective, Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi.*

Introduction

Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi’s work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah fi ilmin-nahw wal-irab” (“Radi’s syntactic commentary on “al-Kafiyah””) is one of the valuable manuscripts preserved in the Manuscripts Fund of the Nakhchivan Branch of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, which began its activities in 2005. “The work, which covers the syntax section of Arabic grammar, was written in 1268 AH (1851 CE)” [5, p. 262]. The book written in the “Nashk” script consists of two parts. The work, which consists of 209 pages (Part I has 94 pages, Part II has 115 pages), is written in Arabic. The margins of the manuscript contain marginal annotations (hashiyas).

In this book written in Arabic by Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi, the science of nahw is explained in a clear and simple language. Distinguished linguist Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti highly praised this work and wrote: “Sharhul-Kafiyah” is not merely a commentary written on a book; rather, it is an independent book of nahw and the product of a sound analysis. Scholars have shown great interest in this book, and it has been widely circulated. Both contemporary and earlier scholars have used it in their studies and works”.

In Part I of the work “Sharhu Radi al-Kafiyah”, there are sections on the Arabic cases of words and sentences: marfuat (sentence members used in the nominative case), mansubat (sentence members used in the accusative case), and majrurat (sentence members used in the genitive case).

In the section on Marfuat (nominative constructions), such sentence elements as the fail (subject), tanazu (syntactic competition between two verbs), naibul-fail (the object of the passive verb), the mubtada (subject of a nominal sentence), the khabar (predicate), khabaru inna wa akhwatiha (the predicate of inna and its sisters), laun-nafiya lil-jins (the predicate of la of absolute negation) and ma wa la mushabbahatani bi-laysa (“ma” and “la” resembling “laysa”), among others, are discussed.

In the section on Mansubat (accusative constructions), the following topics are discussed: maful mutlaq (the Absolute object), hadhful-fil (ellipsis of the verb), maful bihi (direct object), tarhim (intensification of the verb), munada (vocative noun), nida (the vocative particle), hadhf harf al-nida (omission of the vocative particle), ikhtisas (restriction), ishtigal (semantic engagement), tahdhir (warning), maful fih (adverbial of time and place), maful maahu (accompanied object), hal (circumstantial accusative), tamyiz (specification), muthanna (the dual form), khabaru kana wa akhwatiha (the predicate of kana and its sisters), ismu inna wa akhwatiha (the subject of inna and its sisters), la allati li-nafy al-jins (the particle “la” for the negation of genus), and khabaru ma wa la al-mushabbahatayn bi-laysa (the predicate of “ma” and “la” resembling laysa).

In the section on Majrurat (genitive constructions), the following grammatical topics are presented: mudaf ilayhi (the genitive complement in an “idafa” construction), idafa (the genitive construction), al-asma al-sitta (the six nouns), tawabi (dependents), sifa (nat, adjective), tawkid (emphasis) and its types, badal (apposition), atf (coordination), and atf al-bayan (explicative apposition).

Sentence members used in the accusative case (majrurat).

“Words in Arabic grammar are divided into four groups based on changes in word endings and acceptance of inflectional markers (flexion): 1) marfuat (words in the nominative case); 2) mansubat (words in the accusative case (affected, governed)); 3) majrurat (words in the genitive / possessive case); 4) majzum (words in the jussive or shortened form (muzari))” [4, p.76].

“The Majrurat group includes words that occur in the genitive case after the second term of the mudafun ilayhi (idafa construction) or after prepositions.

Words that follow governed elements (mamul) in a syntactic relation and adopt their inflectional markers (irab) are called “tawabi” (dependents). These words adopt the grammatical markers of the preceding words, corresponding to the case categories of nouns and the mood categories of verbs. The tawabi are classified into four categories: sifa (nat) – adjective, atf – coordination (a word connected to the previous word or sentence by a conjunction; predicative combination), tawkid – emphasis (verbal or semantic), badal – apposition / addition. The majzum consists of the imperfect verb (mudari) used in the jussive form after the 14 factors mentioned above” [4, p. 76].

“Nouns and dependents that are required to be in the genitive case due to the preceding words and particles are called majrurat (المجرورات, words in the genitive case). The original nouns that become genitive are the mudaf ilayh (المضاف إليه) and the noun governed by a preposition (الاسم المجرور (بحرف الجر). The sifa, badal, tawkid and matuf (the coordinated element) that depend on them also become genitive” [2, p. 314].

The commentary in the work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah” on the sentence elements used in the genitive case (majrurat) and their irab (inflection).

The discussion of majrurat is explained in a broad sense in the works of Ibn al-Hajib and Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi. While analyzing grammatical topics in his work “Sharhul-kafiyah”, Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi first recalls the grammatical rules established by Ibn al-Hajib and then comments on the subject by adding his own views. In the work, before a new grammatical topic is explained, its title is given at the beginning of the page.

The general meaning of Majrurat (بحث المجرورات):

قوله: المجرورات هو ما اشتمل على عَلمِ المُضَافِ إِلَيْهِ.

The statement of Ibn al-Hajib: “Majrurat means that which carries the sign of the mudaf ilayh” [6, p. 60].

Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi, expressing his opinion on Ibn al-Hajib’s view about the markers of raf (nominative case), nasb (accusative case), and jarr (genitive case), states the following:

The markers of the raf (nominative case) are three things: damma (الضم), alif (الألف), and waw (الواو). For example, as in the words: مُسَلِّمُونَ، أُبُوكَ.

The markers of the nasb (accusative case) are fourthings: fatha (الفتح), kasra (الكسر), alif (الألف), and ya (الياء). For example, as in the words: إِنَّ مُسَلِّمَاتٍ، إِنَّ أَبَاكَ، إِنَّ مُسَلِّمِينَ، إِنَّ مُسَلِّمِينَ.

The markers of the jarr (genitive case) are three things: kasra (الكسرة), fatha (الفتحة), and ya (الياء). For example, as in the words: بِرَيْدٍ، بِأَحْمَدَ، بِمُسْلِمَيْنِ، بِمُسْلِمِينَ، بِأَبِيكَ.

The Topic of “al-Tawabi”(Dependents) in the work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah” (مبحث التَّوَابِعِ)

قوله: كُلُّ ثَانٍ بِإِعْرَابِ سَابِقِهِ مِنْ جِهَةٍ وَاحِدَةٍ.

The statement of Ibn al-Hajib: “Al-Tawabi are every second element (i.e., the following word) that, in one respect, takes the inflection (irab) of the first” [Figure 1]. “Those which do not have an independent inflection but instead follow the inflection of the word they depend on are called al-Tawabi (التَّوَابِعِ – elements dependent in irab)” [2, p. 346]. Al-Tawabi are four: *sifah/nat* (adjective), *tawkid* (emphasis), *badal* (apposition), *atf* (coordination), the latter including *atf al-bayan* (explanatory apposition) and *atf al-nasq* (coordination by conjunction).

Figure 1. The topic of “Tawabi” in the work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah fi ilmin-nahw wal-irab”

The statement of Al-Astarabadi: “In the text of al-Kafiyah, the expression ‘كُلُّ ثَانٍ’ (every second) used by Ibn al-Hajib includes the التَّوَابِعِ, the predicate of the المبتدأ, all predicates belonging to the group of أحوالها, كان, and إِنْ whose original function is the predicate of the mubtada, the (circumstantial accusative), and the second of the two objects of أُعْطِيْتُ and ظَنَنْتُ.”

The author’s statement “بإعراب سابقه” means “with the inflection (irab) of what precedes it”. According to this, the predicate of the المبتدأ, as well as the second objects in the verbs أُعْطِيْتُ and ظَنَنْتُ, are included in this definition. Likewise, words functioning as حال in the accusative – such as in the sentence “ضَرَبْتُ زَيْدًا مُجَرِّدًا” (I struck Zayd while he was alone) – and words functioning as تمييز (specification) in the accusative – such as in the Quranic verse “وَفَجَّرْنَا الْأَرْضَ عُيُونًا” (And We made the earth burst with springs) – are also included in this definition” [3, pp. 81-81^A].

By the phrase “من جهة واحدة” (from one aspect) used by Ibn al-Hajib, Fakhr al-Din al-Razi states that what was mentioned above is excluded from the definition. He maintains that, through the wording of the author (al-musannif), it is shown that the characteristics included within these fall outside the limits of tawabi.

The predicate being in the nominative case “from the perspective of the subject’s nominative status” represents another aspect, namely its being the predicate of the subject. Thus, in the case of the two objects, the accusative of the first is due to its being the first of the two objects, while the accusative of the second is due to its being the second object. Likewise, in the sentence “ضَرَبْتُ زَيْدًا” – I struck Zayd while he was standing”, the first is in the accusative because it is the direct object, whereas the second is in the accusative because it occurs as a “hal”. Similarly, in the sentence “وَفَجَّرْنَا” “الْأَرْضَ عُيُونًا”, the first is in the accusative due to being the direct object, while the second is in the accusative because it functions as tamyiz.

In his work “Sharhul-Kafiyah”, Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi objects to the explanations mentioned by Ibn al-Hajib in his commentary on “al-Kafiyah” with the following words: “This is open to objection, because the nominative status of the subject and the predicate arises from a single aspect, namely that both constitute the essential elements of the sentence. Likewise, the accusative

status of the nouns mentioned above also stems from one aspect, which is that they are فَصَلَاتٌ (adjunct elements)”.

In this matter, Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi proposes the following hypothesis: “If we assume that, for both the first and the second, the change in each noun causes a corresponding change in its respective aspect, then, for example, in the sentence “جَاءَنِي زَيْدٌ الظَّرِيفُ” – The elegant Zayd came to me”, the nominative case of “زَيْدٌ: Zayd” is due to its role as the subject (agent), whereas the accusative case of “الظَّرِيفُ” is due to its functioning as an adjective modifying it.

Similarly, if we consider the other dependent elements (tawabi) in the same way, we are justified in attributing multiple predicates to a single subject. For instance, in the verse “وَهُوَ الْعَفُورُ” – And He is the Most Forgiving, the Loving. The Lord of the Throne, the Lord of honour” (Quran, al-Buruj 85:15-16), several predicates are linked to the same subject. Likewise, in the sentence “عَلِمْتُ زَيْدًا عَاقِلًا ظَرِيفًا” – I considered Zayd learned, intelligent, and refined”, the words coordinated with “عَاقِلًا” illustrate the same principle. Multiple occurrences are also seen in circumstantial constructions, such as “لَا تَجْعَلْ مَعَ اللَّهِ إِلَهًا آخَرَ فَتَقْعُدَ مَذْمُومًا مَخْذُولًا” – Set not up with Allah another god lest thou sit down disgraced and forsaken” (Quran, al-Isra 17:22), where “مَذْمُومًا مَخْذُولًا” function as multiple circumstantial accusatives. Furthermore, exceptions following exceptions, as in “جَاءَنِي الْقَوْمُ إِلَّا زَيْدًا إِلَّا عَمْرًا” – The people came to me except Zayd and except Amr”, exemplify the same syntactic phenomenon.

“After presenting these explanations, al-Razi summarizes his view as follows: the grammatical case of nouns does not change simply because the nouns themselves change, and these should still be included within the definition of tawabi. He further remarks that if Ibn al-Hajib had stated “كُلُّ تَابٍ كُلُّ تَابٍ” – Each second element (tabi) is declined according to the case of the preceding element because of it”, then the objections we have noted would not have arisen” [1, p. 365].

(مبحث النعت) “The Topic of “Nat/Sifah” (Adjective) in the work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah”

قوله: النعت تابع يدل على معنى فشي منبوعه مطلقاً. وقد نبتة تخصيص أو توضيح. وقد يكون لمجرد التثناء، أو الذم، أو التوكيد مثل “نقحة واحدة”. ولا فصل بين أن يكون مشتقاً أو غيره؛
- إذا كان وضعه لعارض المعنى عموماً، مثل “تميمي” و “ذي مال”،
- أو خصوص نحو “مررت برجل أي رجل”، و “بهذا الرجل”، و “يزيد هذا”.
و توصف النكرة بالجملة الخبرية ويلزم الضمير.
ويوصف بحال الموصوف، وبحال متعلقه نحو “مررت برجل حسن غلامه”.
فالأول يتبعه في الإعراب، والتعريف، والتنكير، والإفراد، والتننية، والجمع، والتذكير، والتأنيث.
والثاني يتبعه في الخمسة الأول، وفي البواقي كالفعل؛ ومن ثمه حسن “قام رجل قاعد غلامه”، وضعف “قاعدون غلامه”،
ويجوز “قعود غلامه”.

و الضمير لا يوصف، ولا يوصف به.
والموصوف أخص أو مساو؛ ومن ثمه لم يوصف ذو اللام إلا بمتله أو بالمضاف إلى
مثله.

وإنما التزم وصف باب “هذا” بذي اللام للإبهام، ومن ثمه ضعف “مررت بهذا الأبيض”، وحسن “مررت بهذا العالم”.

The statement of Ibn al-Hajib: “The adjective (nat/sifah) is a dependent element that indicates, in an absolute sense, a meaning inherent in the modified noun” [Figure 2]. The function of the adjective is either specification or determination. Sometimes the adjective occurs merely for praise, satire (blame), or for emphasis, as in the verse “نقحة واحدة” – a single blast”. There is no distinction between the adjective being derived or non-derived. Thus, the expression “قام رجل قاعد غلامه” (A man stood up whose servants are seated) is considered acceptable, whereas “قاعدون غلامه قام رجل” is regarded as weak. However, the example “قعود غلامه قام رجل” is permissible without being judged in terms of elegance or weakness.

A pronoun is not described (i.e., it does not function as a modified noun), nor does it function as an adjective. The modified noun (mawsuf) must be either more specific than, or equal to, the adjective. Accordingly, a noun with the definite article “ال: al” is described only by something similar to it or by a word that is annexed (in an idafa construction) to something similar to it. “The reason why the demonstrative class (the hadha (هذا) group) is described by a noun with the definite article “ال: al” is the inherent vagueness found in demonstrative. Therefore, the expression “مررت

مَرَرْتُ بِهَذَا الْعَالِمِ – I passed by this scholar” is regarded as acceptable” [6, p. 70].

“The adjectival construction is the acquisition of a particular qualification by a noun through the expression that follows it. The construction of a simple adjective consists of two nouns. The first noun is called the modified noun (الموصوف), while the second noun is called the adjective (الصفة). The adjective is also referred to as nat (النعت), and the modified noun (المَوْصُوف) is likewise called manut (المنعوت) [2, p. 347].

Figure 2. The Topic of “Nat/Sifah” (Adjective) in the work “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah fi ilmin-nahw wal-irab”.

Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi explained Ibn al-Hajib’s statement: “وَفَائِدَتُهُ تَخْصِيصٌ أَوْ تَوْضِيحٌ – Its (i.e., the adjective’s) function is specification or clarification”. According to the author’s terminology, specification (takhsis) means “reducing the commonness (or shared reference) that occurs in indefinite nouns”. To explain this point, al-Astarabadi cites the sentence “جَاءَنِي رَجُلٌ صَالِحٌ – A righteous man came to me”, where the word “رَجُلٌ” functions as the subject (fail). In his explanation, the expression “رَجُلٌ”, by virtue of its lexical formation, may potentially refer to any individual belonging to this class. However, when it is described as “صَالِحٌ”: righteous, the element of shared reference and ambiguity associated with the subject is reduced.

Again, al-Razi, interpreting this explanation within the framework of the author’s (Ibn al-Hajib’s) terminology, stated that its meaning is “to eliminate the shared reference that occurs in definite nouns, whether proper or common”. He further argued that this is illustrated in the sentences “رَيْدُ الْعَالِمِ – Zayd the scholar” and “الرَّجُلُ الْفَاضِلُ – the virtuous man”, where the intended effect is the removal of shared reference in the definite noun.

Conclusion

Research shows that the renowned linguist Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi’s work, “Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah fi ilmin-nahw wal-irab” is a valuable written source for the study of Arabic grammar. This work can be regarded as a comprehensive grammatical encyclopaedia that reflects the level of development of the 13th century Arabic linguistic school.

REFERENCES

1. Başçı, A. A Methodological Comparison of the Grammatical Works “SharhuRadi alal-Kafiyah” and “Sharhu Isam alal-Kafiyah”. Bursa: Ekin Press Publishing and Distribution, 2021, 406 p.
2. Çörtü, M. M. Arabic Grammar – Nahw. Istanbul: M.U. Faculty of Theology Foundation Publications, 2005, 454 p.
3. Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi. Sharhu Radi alal-Kafiyah fi Imin-Nahw wal-Irab. In 2 volumes, Vol. I. 1268 AH. Manuscripts Fund of the Nakhchivan Branch of ANAS, Call No.: D-44/264, 94 p.
4. Mammadaliyev, V. M. Arabic Linguistics: A Textbook for Higher Education Institutions. Baku: Maarif, 1985, 288 p.
5. Valiyeva, K. “Sentence Elements Used in the Accusative Case (Mansubat) and Radiyyuddin al-Astarabadi’s Views on This Issue in the Work “Sharhul-Kafiyah”” Scientific Works of the Nakhchivan Branch of ANAS (Series of Social and Humanitarian Sciences), 2024, Vol. 20, No. 1, pp. 262–267.
6. Yanık, N. H. Translation of al-Kafiyah. Istanbul: Muallim Publishing, 2016, 166 p.